

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

TECHNOLOGY OF MASTERING KNOWLEDGE RELATED TO LESSON PLANNING FOR STUDENTS STUDYING AT THE BACHELOR'S LEVEL IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS WITH A PEDAGOGICAL PROFILE

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Abstract

In the article, how lesson planning is understood as a didactic concept, distinguishing its main features, determining dialectical relations with other components of the methodological system, the emergent nature of the educational system of which it is a component, the links of the industrial revolution to the formation of the educational space, the paradigm of management, the elements of shared experience (a necessary part), the attention is focused on the dependence of the expected results, standards, spatial situation of those who interact in the designed process (the teacher and the learner), and the capacity load of natural and artificial intelligence. It is said that the existence of said arguments is related to the fact that the lesson is a form of action. The quality of a lesson, which is considered as a form of action, is determined by its conformity to standards, norms, the demands of social and economic development, the interests of the state, society, and the main functioning entity.

In the article, examples are presented in order to create a visual basis for students' assimilation of considerations related to lesson planning.

Keywords: learning process; component; methodological system; content and form; dialectical unity; stages of the lesson; expected result; standard; management paradigm.

Relevance of the research topic. It is indisputable that a person engaged in teaching uses natural intelligence (specialist) forms of education in his pedagogical activity. The shared material becomes a movement by some methods and creates a specific form, which we do not object to calling this form of movement "lesson". It is a component of the social process - the educational system, designed for the purpose of management. Since the process of improvement of the system to which it belongs is a perennial didactic problem, the problem of developing its adequate projects is also perennial. The acquisition of the experience of the student (tomorrow's teacher) to design management forms of training approaches subject to continuous changes based on the logic of rational thinking, it is necessary to master the theoretical foundations of the mentioned practice. One of the urgent didactic issues is the mastery of the technology of developing lesson projects by students based on the selected training approaches, showing the way to turn relevant knowledge into skills. Therefore, we claim the relevance of the research topic.

Interpretation of generalizations on research materials. As is known, training is one of the main concepts of pedagogy. Although training is an important characteristic of educational activity, it does not cover all aspects of it. Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. However, learning and learning activities are essentially different events. Appropriation is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every field of activity. Teaching activity is a type of activity, a unique form of social activity of the personality. [3;150]

Prof. According to ANAbasov, training has complex educational-educational-developmental functions.

In training, there are two sides: teaching and learning. The effectiveness of training depends to a large extent on the correct interaction of teachers and students in the teaching process, the level of cognitive activity and independence of students, and their interest in learning. Learning depends on the characteristics of the personality, including those that direct it to the future. It is an appropriate process resulting from actions. [1; 210]

From the analysis of scientific sources, it is clear that at the beginning of the 20th century, the concept of "training" included the two components that make up this process - the concepts of teaching and learning. Teaching is understood as the activity of teachers to organize the learning of lesson material. Learning refers to the activity of students to master the material. The managerial activity of the teacher to form the cognitive activity of the students, the joint activity of the teacher and the students is also reflected in the concept of training [12; 132]

By summarizing the information we have worked on based on the data we have collected, we emphasize that the dialectical relations of the training process, its components (including the organizational form), the improvement of the "enabling functions" of each component, and the realization of its functions in the educational space adequately formed to the convocations of industrial revolutions are important in solving the actual problems. Taking advantage of the "system-structure" approach is one of the reliable ways out.

We also know that it is necessary to mention that the training system means a whole, complete institution selected according to certain criteria. Training systems are characterized by the internal integrity and com-

pleteness of the structures created by the unity of training, education goals, regularities, organizational principles, content, forms and methods. [7; 266-268]

The 21st century is the century of globalization. Therefore, 21st century skills should be taken into account in the content of education. In addition to knowledge, the development of abilities and skills such as complex problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, leadership, digital literacy, emotional intelligence, global citizenship, collaboration, discussion, judgment and decision-making will also be considered key learning outcomes. [13-14;330-343]

It is known that changes in industry and technology have necessitated the restructuring of educational institutions in every era to meet the needs of society as well as the workforce required by various sectors. In line with the industrial revolution, education has also undergone a process of development from Education 1.0 to Education 4.0. Education 4.0 serves to prepare individuals who will operate in the global and digital work environment during the IV industrial revolution. Education 4.0 is an educational system that provides continuous learning from childhood to school, from there to working life, and allows to take an important place in the world and make changes. [15;25-30-16;558-564]

Education 4.0 should serve the formation of the skills of using new technologies that help the development of students in accordance with the changes in society, the knowledge and skills that can be used throughout their life should be formed in the students, not just reading and writing [16; 558-564]. The system in question must respond to changes in the social and economic environment to meet the need for human capital. Education 4.0 aims to prepare individuals to be creative and innovative.

In the Education 4.0 approach, going beyond the constructivist educational systems and Bloom's technology, it is determined that an educational process based on the following areas will be implemented:

- 1) 3R regulating understanding (Recalling, Relating, Refining);
- 2) 3I (Inquiring, Interacting, Interpreting-Explaining) that encourages research;
- 3) Conclusion-based 3P (Participating, Processing, Presenting).

In the era of the IV industrial revolution, "smart" educational tools and resources should allow individuals to acquire more perfect experience, knowledge and skills, and reveal their innovative perspectives.[17;92-97]

It can be argued that the current educational system in accordance with modern didactics transforms various sub-system types and sub-types into itself. Among them problem training, algorithmic training, programmed training, active training, integrative training, developmental training, cooperative training, inclusive training, etc. can be attributed. By the way, let's note that differences of opinion among educators are not absent in the comments given about "training types", "training approaches", "subsystems of training".

The concept of "methodical system" has a special place among the important concepts in modern didactics. Methodical system is conditioned by the dialectic between goal, content, means (resource), method, form of organization and result [2]. The improvement of the management of the educational process depends to a great extent on the interpretation of the theoretical and practical foundations of the system of its organizational forms, the didactic connections and dependencies of this system with other educational components.

A unified opinion on the interpretation of the concept of the form of organization of training has not yet been fully and definitively formed. However, "there is no one against considering the form of organization of training as its component. In our opinion, it should be understood as "the mode of existence of the content of training (the process of change and development, the system based on the paradigm of "opportunity-movement-new quality"), its own internal organization and structure that makes it possible for the content to exist." In other words, the concept of "organizational form", which is among the elements of the methodical system, can be understood as a form of cognitive movement of the group (students) included in the training system, which contains the training material that has become a cognitive movement as a content. It should be emphasized that in such an approach, the teaching method can be interpreted as a form of movement of the teaching material.

The effectiveness of managing the learning process, which is a complete system, depends on finding the right balance between its content and form. Training practice has confirmed that the main organizational form of training and education work in secondary schools is the lesson. "The lesson is such an organizational form of training that ensures the content, principles and methods of training, is planned and regulated by the teacher within a certain time frame, and appears as a set of teacher-student relations" [5; 232].

Psychologists rightly emphasize that the lesson should be modern not only in terms of its scientific-theoretical level, but also in terms of its pedagogical concept - its construction with new dimensions of pedagogical thinking [6;147]

It is undeniable that a group of teachers currently working in secondary schools have benefited from the traditional training model for a long time and have achieved considerable success. Therefore, it is not acceptable to completely abandon this model. It is good that the advantages of the so-called traditional training model are taken into account in modern training approaches.

Here, we believe that it is necessary to direct students' attention to the thematic and lesson planning related to the mentioned training model. The resulting study Our generalizations based on the materials suggest that this presentation has a positive effect on the general preparation of students.

Sections of the thematic plan according to the traditional training model.

1. The topic of the lesson (or lessons) is taken from the program.

1.1. The purpose of the lessons or the didactic purpose of the topic (Which comes from the content of the planned topic. This can be expressed in a general way in the thematic plan).

1.2. Lesson types (One or more types are indicated according to the content of the training material and the purpose of the lessons).

1.3. Methods of training (Only general methods are shown in the thematic plan).

2. Actualization.

This section of the plan is defined by the work process itself:

2.1. What pre-learned concepts should be updated;

2.2. What type of independent work should be performed (independent work that updates previous knowledge and deepens what has already been mastered is determined).

3. Formation of new concepts and methods of action.

This section shows:

3.1. New concepts included in this topic (or unknown signs of previously included concepts);

3.2. Increase of students' intended knowledge, skills and habits in the lesson (or several lessons) and homework;

3.3. The main problem of the lesson (or several lessons).

4. Implementation.

The content of this section of the thematic plan shows:

4.1. Independent types of work aimed at synthesizing newly learned material with material learned in previous lessons at different levels and options;

4.2. Necessary interdisciplinary communication for the formation of the system of knowledge and worldview.

5. Homework. The task includes:

5.1. Material for repetition from the textbook and other information sources;

5.2. Types of independent work for preparation for the next lesson.

Traditional lesson planning.

The contents of the sections of the plan include:

1. The topic of the lesson (usually taken from the thematic plan without modification).

1.1. The purpose of the lesson (determined on the basis of the content of the program material);

1.2. Type of lesson (it is as indicated in the thematic plan, specified by the teacher as a subtype);

1.3. Training methods (specified, learning and teaching methods are shown);

1.4. Means of training (training methods and tools are planned according to the types of lessons).

2. The transformation of the goals and tasks set before the lesson (formulated by the teacher) into the student's cognitive goal (the object of satisfying cognitive needs).

2.1. Knowledge and activity methods intended to be acquired are determined by understanding their practical and theoretical importance and usefulness for teaching or other activities;

2.2. Methods and tools that create cognitive interest in students with fun, surprising and other aspects are chosen;

2.3. The ways of choosing and applying the means of putting students in a problem situation and formulating the purpose of the lesson in the form of a problem are defined;

3. Actualization.

3.1. Depending on the type and purpose of the lesson, the complexity of the concept and activity methods to be actualized, the time spent on actualization is determined;

3.2. Reference knowledge. The teacher determines the knowledge (previously learned) that should be activated in the student's mind with the necessary connections and relationships;

3.2.1. Plans students' written or oral independent work (frontal);

3.2.2. Methods of arousing students' interest in the topic and lesson, forming motives are selected;

3.2.3. During the course of the work, the form of control is determined, the principles of self-control of students, their mutual control, ways to perform independent tasks, to evaluate knowledge, skills and habits are provided.

4. Formation of new concepts and methods of action.

4.1. New concepts, skills, habits and methods of their mastery that are necessary to be learned in the lesson are selected and shown in the plan;

4.2. The cognitive tasks of the mastery stages are formulated;

4.3. The teacher formulates the problematic and informative questions that he will put before the students, and from among them, the questions that will be proposed to the students in order to create a problematic situation are determined;

4.4. The main and additional problems of the lesson are indicated, the options for solving them are formulated (analytical and heuristic solutions).

5. Application.

The skills and habits shown in section 4 are reinforced in the lesson (independent application of acquired knowledge is considered the main way).

5.1. The teacher shows specific skills and habits for development;

5.2. The plan shows the types of independent work as well as the type.

6. Conclusion of the lesson.

6.1. On the basis of the set goal (during the course of the lesson), it is intended to evaluate the activity and results of the students, to ensure generalization and psychological completeness.

6.2. Assessment and justification of students' knowledge is planned.

7. Giving tasks to students to work at home.

The rules for planning recommendations for the work of each student are defined. [4; 207-209]

The teachers who have won the public's approval with their success focused on the following main issues while preparing for the lesson and planning. Our pedagogical research led us to this conclusion:

1. Pre-workout;

2. Defining a common goal;
3. Active determination of students' understanding and needs;
4. Determination of adapted assistance;
5. Supporting the implementation of the goal;
6. Creating feedback;
7. Frustration and risk management;
8. Help with independence and generalization to other contexts.

Daily planning based on subject curricula

1. Determine the expected results of the lesson (determine the learning results of the lesson based on the sub-standard);
2. Determine what conclusions (generalizations) the students will reach at the end of the lesson;
3. Preparing the motivation of the lesson (creating a problem situation, choosing the type of motivation, setting the research question correctly);
4. Identify sources of knowledge used to collect new knowledge during research;
5. Develop research tasks that can lead to the specified expected results;
6. Determine research methods;
7. Prepare the necessary materials and worksheets, determine the presentation form of the research;
8. Articulating guiding questions used during discussion;
9. Systematization of information (scheme, formula, graph, table, project, etc.);
10. Prepare additional information, tasks, taking into account the assumed new results;
11. Determine the time for each phase of the lesson;
12. Preparing tasks for the creative application phase of the lesson;
13. Choosing the evaluation form (method), defining the criteria;
14. Determine the course of reflection based on the needs of teachers and students;
15. Determine the technical means to be used in the lesson;
16. Prepare stationery to be used in the lesson. [6;245]

Active lesson plan(schematic)

Subject:(the name of the topic is written).

Standard:(sub-standard or sub-standards are mentioned).

Purpose:(goals are listed clearly and concisely).

Work form:(for example, written in pairs, small or large groups, frontal, etc.).

Working method:(eg discussion, derivation of understanding).

Resources:(e.g. various pictures, manual, calculation, measuring tools, etc.).

Course of the lesson

I stage (Motivation, setting the problem)

Auxiliary questions: -----

Research questions:-----

Phase II: (Conducting research)

Worksheet 1. ----- Worksheet 2. -----

Worksheet 3.-----

III stage:(information exchange).

IV stage:(discussion of information):

Discussion questions:-----

Stage V:(conclusion and summary).

VI stage:(creative app).

Stage VII: (evaluation or reflection).

Note:

- To plan a lesson, it is important to coordinate all its components;
- The learning outcomes of the lesson should be directly related to the tasks. Based on the generalizations, the research question of the lesson is formulated. All this ensures the completeness and systematicity of the lesson (close connection between the beginning and the end of the lesson) and serves to achieve learning outcomes.

Let's give examples that illustrate our point.

Subject: Addition and subtraction of mixed numbers.

Standard: 1.2.4.Performs calculations on ordinary and decimal fractions;

Training result: Adds and subtracts mixed numbers with different denominators;

Work form: Collective and group work;

Method of work: Brainstorming, discussion;

Resource: Textbook, ICT equipment, worksheets.

Course of the lesson

First lesson:The teacher is on the board

$2\frac{5}{12} + 3\frac{1}{12}$ writes the example and "What kind of

numbers are these numbers and how can the addition be performed?" - he addresses the class. Students are already able to add mixed numbers with the same denominator from the V grade mathematics course[10-11]. After listening to the opinion of the students, the example is solved by the students on the board. The teacher calls out the research question.

Research question:How to add and subtract mixed numbers with different denominators?

Conducting research: The class is divided into 4 groups. Each group is given a worksheet corresponding to the examples below.

Examples of worksheets[9]:

I.To add mixed numbers:
 1) fractional parts of these numbers _____
 2) integers _____ and fractional parts of mixed numbers _____
 3) if the fractional part _____ fraction is taken, it is _____
 We convert _____ and add it to the previous _____ number.

II. Instead of an asterisk, type:
 a) $2\frac{2}{5} + 7\frac{3}{10} = * + \frac{*}{10} + \frac{3}{10} = * \frac{7}{10} 6\frac{7}{8} + 3\frac{5}{12} = * + \frac{*}{24} + \frac{*}{24} = * \frac{*}{24}$;
 c) $-5 = ; 9\frac{1}{2} - 5\frac{9}{17} = 9\frac{**}{**} - 5\frac{*}{*} = * \frac{*}{*}$

III. Do the operations by converting a decimal fraction to a regular fraction:
 a) $3,25 + 12\frac{3}{11} =$ b) $18\frac{13}{41} - 6,5 =$

I. To subtract mixed numbers:
 1. Fractional parts of these numbers _____
 2. If the fractional part of the subtraction is smaller than the fractional part of the subtraction, then _____
 3. The whole of the subtracted from the whole of the decrement _____ From the fraction of the decrement, we subtract _____ of the subtractor.

II. Instead of an asterisk, type:
 a) $1\frac{5}{6} + 9\frac{1}{12} = 1\frac{*}{12} + 9\frac{1}{12} = * \frac{*}{12} + \frac{1}{12} = 10\frac{*}{12}$
 b) $5\frac{11}{14} + 4\frac{6}{21} = * \frac{*}{42} + \frac{*}{42} = * \frac{*}{42} = * \frac{3}{42}$
 c) $19\frac{1}{3} - 15\frac{5}{7} = 19\frac{**}{**} - 15\frac{*}{*} = 4\frac{**}{**} = 3\frac{**}{**} = 3\frac{*}{*}$

III. Do the operations by converting a decimal fraction to a regular fraction:
 a) $5,15 + 7\frac{3}{25} =$ b) $12\frac{13}{31} - 9,5 =$

Presentation: Each group representative writes his task and its solution is discussed. Here, the student must separate whole and fractional parts, and after bringing wholes to one and fractions to a common denominator, add or subtract.

When presenting each group task, the teacher can give necessary directions.

Thus, after completing the above tasks, groups clarify how to add and subtract mixed numbers with different denominators.

Work: Let's calculate by converting decimal fractions to ordinary fractions:

a) $4,25 + 1\frac{19}{25} = 4\frac{25}{100} + 1\frac{76}{100} = 6\frac{1}{100}$

b)

$7\frac{7}{8} - 3,18 = 7\frac{7}{8} - 3\frac{18}{100} = 7\frac{175}{200} - 3\frac{36}{200} = 4\frac{139}{200}$

The second lesson. During this lesson, according to the textbook [8; 29] It will be useful to perform exercises No. 9-16 (or in this part).

Work. To solve this task, the class is divided into groups. Each group tries to reveal the name of the Azerbaijani scientist while completing the task. The task is:

• According to the table, explain the name of the Azerbaijani scientist (arrange the sequence of letters according to the serial numbers of the tasks).

I. $4\frac{7}{27} - 2\frac{2}{9}$; VI. $\frac{2}{11} + \frac{7}{22} + 5\frac{2}{44}$;

II. $6\frac{11}{48} + \frac{17}{24}$; VII. $\frac{25}{49} - \frac{1}{7} - \frac{5}{14}$;

III. $7\frac{61}{81} - \frac{1}{18}$; VIII. $9,05 - 4\frac{3}{5}$;

IV. $0,625 + 6\frac{9}{16}$; IX. $47\frac{7}{8} - 45\frac{15}{52}$;

v. $7,8 + \frac{39}{50}$;

Table 1

Answer	$7\frac{113}{162}$	8,58	$2\frac{1}{27}$	$5\frac{3}{16}$	$5\frac{6}{10}$	4,45	$6\frac{15}{16}$	$2\frac{17}{104}$	$\frac{1}{98}$
Letter	T	I	L	F	Z	D	U	A	A

• When solving the task, you can announce a competition between groups;

• The letters of the scientist's name are arranged according to the serial number of the tasks.

Suggested work for individual implementation:

$\left(20 - 10\frac{23}{36}\right) - \left(14\frac{4}{27} - 6\frac{1}{18}\right)$

Similar to this, the following works are given as homework:

Calculate:

- a) $5\frac{5}{9} + 3\frac{1}{6} - 6\frac{4}{27}$;
 b) $12\frac{13}{48} - \left(9\frac{17}{32} - 4\frac{5}{24}\right)$;
 c) $1\frac{5}{7} + 3\frac{11}{14} - 2\frac{1}{4}$;
 d) $\left(18 - 10\frac{18}{35}\right) - \left(3\frac{9}{28} + 2\frac{3}{20}\right)$;

In addition, it is given as homework:

Task 1. To write three articles on the computer $53\frac{4}{10}$ minutes have been spent. First and second article together $25\frac{14}{15}$ minutes, and to the second and

third articles together $38\frac{19}{45}$ minutes were spent, how much time was spent on each article?

Task 2. To prepare 12 kg of dough $7\frac{4}{15}$ kg of flour,

$2\frac{11}{20}$ kg fat, $1\frac{23}{30}$ kg of powdered sugar and some juice were used. Determine the mass of the juice.

The following problem is solved as a class work:

The issue. In three crates $36\frac{9}{16}$ There are kg of

oranges. Together in the first and second crate $28\frac{7}{8}$ kg,

and in the second and third crate together $24\frac{3}{4}$ kg of

oranges, how many kg of oranges are in each crate? In solving this issue, it is appropriate to build a model according to the condition:

Scheme 1

$$28\frac{7}{8} \qquad 24\frac{3}{4}$$

Solution: First, let's find how many oranges are in box III. For this, it is necessary to subtract the mass of the orange in boxes I and II from the mass of the orange in box 3:

$$36\frac{9}{16} - 28\frac{7}{8} = 36\frac{9}{16} - 28\frac{14}{16} = 7\frac{11}{16} (kg)$$

By the same rule in box I:

$$36\frac{9}{16} - 24\frac{3}{4} = 36\frac{9}{16} - 24\frac{12}{16} = 11\frac{13}{16} (kg);$$

$$\text{In box II: } 7\frac{11}{16} + 11\frac{13}{16} = 18\frac{24}{16} = 19\frac{8}{16} (kg);$$

$$36\frac{9}{16} - 19\frac{8}{16} = 17\frac{1}{16} (kg).$$

$$\text{Answer: } 11\frac{13}{16} kg; 17\frac{1}{16} kg; 7\frac{11}{16} kg.$$

Summary and conclusion: The procedure for adding and subtracting mixed numbers is repeated and summarized. Here, the special cases encountered are emphasized again.

Points to note: The teacher should pay attention to the fact that it is difficult for students to understand addition and subtraction in cases where the fractional part received during the addition of mixed numbers is in the form of an improper fraction and the fractional part of the decrement is smaller than the fractional part of the subtrahend. Table 2.

Stages		
I stage	II stage	III stage
Difficulty performing addition and subtraction of mixed numbers with different denominators.	Adds mixed numbers with different denominators to the same denominator, but has difficulty subtracting.	Freely adds and subtracts mixed numbers with different denominators.

Evaluation. Implementation.

The topic can be taught in several lessons instead of one. These lessons can have a single structure. Tasks applied at any stage should follow each other logically so that the student's mental activity (and practical activity based on it) is directed towards the goal. For example, it is possible that the post-generalization

process is carried out in the second lesson devoted to the topic.

Let's take a look at the lesson examples so that our idea becomes clearer.

Subject: Proportion.

Standard: 1.2.5. Solves simple problems involving ratio, proportion, directly proportional, inversely proportional quantities and percentages.

Learning outcome: Solves simple proportion problems.

Work form: Collective and group work.

Working method: Cluster and discussion.

Resource: Textbook, ICT equipment, worksheets.

Course of the lesson

First lesson. Setting the problem. The teacher draws a circle on the blackboard with "numbers with a ratio of 7" (or presents it with the computer). Students write numbers with a ratio of 7 around it. Of course, there are many such numbers. The teacher says that it is enough to write a few of them.

Scheme 2

Teacher: "Children, as you can see, the number of such ratios is infinite, and since they are equal to the same number, these ratios can be equated to each other." $49 : 7 = 0,7 : 0,1$ or $14 : 2 = 70 : 10$ and so on.

Research question: How is the basic property of proportion expressed?

Teacher's comment: The teacher says that such equations are called ratios. Since it is a new concept, the word "Proportion" is written on the board (or displayed on the computer screen). The literal spelling of the ratio, the average and outer limits are determined,

and the teacher informs about them. It is important to bring both spellings to the students' attention: $a : b =$

$$c : d; \frac{a}{b} = \frac{c}{d}$$

Conducting research: The class is divided into several groups. The teacher gives each of them worksheets with proportion-related tasks written on them. Instructs you to find the product of outliers and medians.

Examples for worksheets:

No. 1

<p>1. Write the extreme and middle limits of the given ratio: $n : k = m : p$ Outliers _____ Average limits _____</p> <p>2. Are the given proportions proportional? a) $13 : 8 = 26 : 16$; b) $15 : 25 = 3 : 5$ c) $54 : 108 = 0,5 : 7$; c) $65 : 7 = 13 : 35$</p>	<p>3. Write the extremes and middle limits in the given proportion and find their product: a) $1\frac{3}{5} : \frac{13}{5} = \frac{2}{13} : \frac{1}{4}$ Outer limits _____ Their output _____ Average limits _____ Their output _____</p>
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No. 2.

<p>1. Write the extreme and middle limits of the given ratio: $c : r = h : m$ Outer Limits _____ Average limits _____</p> <p>2. Are the given proportions proportional? a) $3 : 19 = 6 : 38$; b) $45 : 55 = 9 : 11$ c) $48 : 22 = 65 : 75$; c) $95 : 17 = 17 : 95$</p>	<p>3. Write the extremes and middle limits in the given proportion and find their product: a) $1\frac{1}{7} : 2\frac{3}{7} = \frac{2}{3} : \frac{5}{4}$ Outliers _____ Their product _____ Average limits _____ Their product _____</p>
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Group representatives present their work. The products of the extremes and averages are compared. Thus, the main property of proportion emerges. Teacher: "Children, now let's determine the importance of the main property of proportion." For this, the first nine exercises in the textbook [8; 45-46] can be performed during the first lesson. This is very helpful. It is advisable to give similar tasks as homework. By completing these tasks, the equation and their solutions are also remembered. The rules for finding the unknown divisor and divisor are mentioned.

Work. It is convenient to apply the basic property of proportion to find the unknown in the equation.

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{d) } 4,9 : 0,35 = a : 35 \\ 0,35 \cdot a = 4,9 \cdot 35 \\ 0,35 \cdot a = 171,5; a = 490 \\ b = 35 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{e) } \frac{108}{90} = \frac{42}{b} \\ 108 \cdot b = 42 \cdot 90 \\ b = 3780 : 108; \\ b = 35 \end{array}$$

Points to note: Students find it difficult to match, mainly due to the interpretation of the problem. Writing the appropriate quantities under each other is one of the important points in solving the problem by establishing a ratio. A student who performs this writing correctly will also be able to establish the proportion correctly. Therefore, the teacher should be able to correctly guide the student in solving the problem of proportion.

The second lesson. During this lesson, work is done on tasks with a relatively high level of difficulty.

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{c) } 2,5x : 14 = \frac{1}{7} : 30 \\ 2,5x \cdot 30 = 14 \cdot \frac{1}{7} \\ 75x = 2 \\ x = \frac{2}{75} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{d) } \frac{2}{x-0,4} = \frac{1}{0,4} \\ x-0,4 = 2 \cdot 0,4 \\ x = 1,2 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{e) } 36 : 35 = \frac{1}{5} x : \frac{1}{12} \\ \frac{1}{5} x \cdot 35 = 36 \cdot \frac{1}{12} \\ 7x = 3 \\ x = \frac{3}{7} \end{array}$$

Study No. 13 is similar to exercise No. 12, so it can be given as homework. During the third lesson, it is appropriate to complete exercises No. 15-20 from the textbook. These tasks are solved by applying the "whole-part" model, as well as establishing proportions based on the condition of the problem.

Exercise 14. 4220 g of semolina, 960 g of milk and 50 g of powdered sugar were taken to prepare porridge

$$\text{Splitting: } 4 : 18 = 220 : x$$

$$\text{Milk: } 4 : 18 = 960 : y$$

$$\text{Sugar: } 4 : 18 = 50 : z$$

the proportions are solved:

$$x = 990 \text{ g; } y = 4320 \text{ g; } z = 225 \text{ g.}$$

4 people - 220 g of buckwheat 18 people - xg groats
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4 people - 50 g of powdered sugar 18 people - sugar powder

4 people - 960 g of milk 18 people - yq milk

The works covered by No. 10-17 of the textbook [8] are performed during this lesson. Doing tasks in groups is appropriate.

The construction of the ratio according to the given equation in Exercise 10 is designed for the development of logical thinking. Here's how it works: $4 \cdot 9 = 18 \cdot 2$ What ratio can you correct from the equation?

In Exercise 11, based on the equality of the given ratios, students should write numbers in place of a and b so that the correct equality is obtained. For this, they must be able to use the basic property of fractions. c)

$$\frac{7}{a} = \frac{48}{b}, \text{ where if we change the denominator of the}$$

fraction on the right by the numerator of the fraction on the left side, the equality in the ratio will not be

violated: $\frac{b}{a} = \frac{48}{7}$. In this proportion, if we multiply

the numerator and denominator of the fraction on the right side of the equation by any natural number, for

example, 2, then $\frac{96}{14} = \frac{48}{7}$ we will buy. So, a=14,

b=96 it can be. In a special case, a=7, b=48, can also be taken.

In study No. 12, the root of equations is found by using the main property of proportion.

for one person. How much of each of these foods should be taken to make porridge for 18 people?

Apparently, the number of people increased from 4 people to 18 people. Therefore, semolina, milk, sugar powder have been increased in the same proportion. That is, based on the condition of the problem, we can establish the following correspondences.

Creative application: Exercise № 20 can be done: Ali measured the height of the classroom and found it to be 2.5 m. The ratio of the heights of the room, the door and the window accordingly 5 : 3 : 2 is like Find the height of the window and door. The ratio of the height of the room to the height of the door 5 : 3 is like

It is useful to solve the problem by constructing a whole-part model. The process is supposed to be carried out independently by students.

Answer: The height of the door is 1.5 m, the height of the window is 1 m.

Evaluation. Implementation.

Table 3.

Levels		
I level	Level II	Level III
He knows the main property of proportion, but cannot apply it in problem solving.	He builds proportions according to the condition of the case, and it is difficult to solve.	He applies the main property of proportion with examples, constructs and solves a proportion according to the problem.

The result. 1) The preparation of the plan (project) of the lesson, which aims at the expected results (conditions the transformation of the goal into a result), depends on how it is understood as a didactic concept (to which categorical concept or apparatus it belongs): it is accepted that the lesson is a form of cognitive action of the group; 2) The level of efficiency of the project of the lesson is high when its main features are correctly distinguished; dialectical relations with other components of the methodical system are defined; from the emergent nature of the training system of which it is a component, the references of the industrial revolution to the formation of the educational space, the paradigm of management, the elements of the shared experience (the necessary part), the expected results, standards, the spatial situation of those who interact in the designed process (learner and teacher), attention is focused on the dependence of natural and artificial intelligence on the "carrying load"; 3) The quality of the lesson, which is considered as a form of movement, is determined by its compliance with standards, norms, requirements of social and economic development, the interests of the state, society and the person with the main component function.

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